

INVESTIGATING PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS IN PAKISTANI POLITICAL MEMOIRS

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ABSTRACT

Perception and interpretation of presupposition triggers depend on the use of pragmatic context. For some decades, many researchers have explored these triggers to reveal the implicit meanings of utterances. This article explores the types and functions of presupposition triggers used in Pakistani political memoirs. Two Pakistani political memoirs, *Pakistan: A personal history* by Imran Khan and *In the Line of Fire: A memoir* by Pervaiz Musharaf, were explored according to the model of George Yule (1996). A corpus pragmatic approach with mixed method research was selected for the present study, and through AntConc 3.5 the types of presupposition triggers were selected. The functions of these triggers were analyzed qualitatively. The findings revealed that both writers pointed towards different political events through different presupposition triggers. The results also showed that existential and factive presupposition triggers were used at the maximum level in both memoirs. Counterfactual conditionals, lexical presupposition triggers, structural presupposition triggers, and non-factive items were used in descending order. It was found that functions of these presupposition triggers in political memoirs aroused different assumptions. At the same time, a few differences were also found in both of the memoirs; however, they were not very significant. Mainly they trigger political and personal functions in the texts.

Keywords: presupposition triggers, contextual influence, political memoirs

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I. INTRODUCTION

Employing presupposition triggers in political genres to share more political or nonpolitical information has remained a debatable issue for researchers. Politicians utilized these presupposition triggers in their speeches to attract their readers' attention so they could bring political events in their readers' notice more while neglecting others (Verovšek, 2016). It has been observed that understanding of these triggers enables readers to recognize the clear motives of the writers towards an incident (Liang & Yabin Liu, 2016). Therefore, researchers are urged to investigate these presupposition triggers to describe the accurate picture of their use in various political genres. Previously, the examination of presupposition trigger was performed in newspaper political speeches and articles. Researchers explored these triggers to reveal the implicit meanings of utterances found in speeches. It is observed that politicians deliver speeches with some hidden intentions, and being a part of language properties, presupposition triggers make political discourse exciting and attractive for the audience while explaining those hidden intentions to them (Fadhly & Kurnia, 2015). For example, Liang & Lie (2016) investigated presupposition triggers in numerous political speeches of American and British presidents to explain their intended meanings. Similarly, newspaper articles were explored through these presupposition triggers by Khaleel in 2010, Fadhly & Kurnia in 2015, and by Sinta et al., (2016). However, among the list of genres, other political genres are also available to be explored from this point of view.

This research paper adopted a corpus pragmatic approach to analyzing these presupposition triggers in another political genre: memoirs. A memoir, a subcategory of autobiography, is a story "from a person's life". Memoirs vary from autobiographies because autobiographies explain and justify one's life actions (Reece, 2014), while memoirs can either be about those events from one's life or someone known to the writer. Researchers' analysis covered two Pakistani politician memoirs: "Pakistan: A Personal History" by Imran Khan and "In the line of Fire" by Pervaiz

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Musharaf. The writers of these memoirs are well recognized political personalities of Pakistan, so their memoirs were selected for analysis. The focus of the study was on types of presupposition triggers used in the memoirs of Imran Khan and Pervaiz Musharaf to investigate their functions. This study adopted a mixed-method research design. The software tool AntConc 3.5.8 was used to collect and accumulate presupposition triggers from both political memoirs. They were discussed thoroughly in a qualitative manner. All six types of presupposition triggers presented by Yule (1996) were explored and discussed from these memoirs. The research paper findings revealed that the functions of presupposition triggers exhibited political and personal use at the maximum level from both the memoirs. Being part of the political genre, the writers politically covered events in both memoirs; however, personal events were also covered at maximum level in both memoirs.

Presupposition triggers are used to trigger implicit meanings of the sentences. Therefore, politicians use them in their memoirs to provide a particular shade (political or nonpolitical) to an event. The types and functions of presupposition triggers can vary in the memoirs. So, the problem of this study was to investigate what kinds of presupposition triggers were utilized in the selected memoirs and to explore their functions contextually. The present study has the following objectives:

- 1: To identify the types of presupposition triggers used by Pakistani writers in their political memoirs.
- 2: To explore the function of these presupposition triggers.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The theoretical background of the present study was based on George Yule's (1996) theory of presupposition triggers. Six presupposition triggers existential, lexical, factive, non-factive, structural, and counterfactual conditionals are the main components of his theory. These triggers were investigated to explore their functions in both memoirs.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Presupposition triggers are mostly explored to comprehend the hidden meanings of the writers' discourse. Every discourse has its own goals and objectives, and understanding of discourse is not built merely on the knowledge of grammar (Your Dictionary). The study of lexical and structural presupposition triggers enables readers to recognize writers' motives (Fillmore, 1969). For decades, writers have been using presupposition triggers to plant their ideas in their discourses because these triggers are helpful in providing information about the writers' intentions. Several writers have investigated presupposition triggers as assumptions behind the surface forms of sentences, so Levinson (1983) has prescribed the name of semantic presupposition to them. Semantic presupposition offers surface-level structure description. For Grundy (2008), semantic presupposition provides a sense of an utterance through information, and the presupposition is triggered by such forms: wh-questions, embedded wh-constructions, definite description, and lexical item. Other structures also give rise to the presupposition, such as iterative, temporal clauses, change of state verbs, clefts, and implicative verbs. So, semantic presupposition deals with the surface of the sentences.

Another utilization of this term is the exploration of presupposition triggers within their contexts called pragmatic presupposition. According to Levinson (1983), the understanding of pragmatic presupposition is challenging because it is a blend of context with its participants. The understanding of a sentence's meaning becomes easy if we judge its context. Presupposition helps readers to comprehend sentences' inexplicit meanings with their contexts (Smailhyeen & Latiff, 2018). For Grundy (2008), pragmatic presupposition is a proper understanding of a statement through context. Regarding the discussion mentioned above, another essential point of consideration is arisen: whether to treat presupposition semantically or pragmatically as both ideologies have some limitations. We become confused while using presupposition pragmatically, as we are not sure about the authenticity of the context. On the other hand, sometimes structure and form do not trigger a presupposition in semantic presupposition. So, some writers said that both could be used according to the need and nature of the study.

In negation of separate treatment of presupposition triggers, some writers debate that these triggers cannot be explored in isolation. For example, sometimes only a linguistic form is required to understand the meaning of an utterance, and sometimes, context is essential to comprehend that meaning completely (Grundy, 2008). The mingling of content with context provides a better understanding of the text (Stalnaker, 1973). Stalnaker further adds that these are the shared assumptions between the participants of a particular discourse, and they underlie the surface content of discourse, so their understanding is essential to grasp the meanings of the text. Levinson (1983) summed up the discussion in these words that presupposition is based on semantic and pragmatic interactions. The indication

of any specific event is mainly done through expressions (Strawson, 1950), and when these expressions indicate presupposition, they are called presupposition triggers. Yule (1996) has presented his theory of presupposition triggers, having six components. The detail of these triggers is mentioned below.

III.I. EXISTENTIAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS

Existential presupposition triggers comprise the definite noun phrase. They are part of the possessive noun phrases and definite noun construction (Yule, 1996). With the help of these triggers, we get information about the mentioned entities (Zare et al., 2012).

III.II. LEXICAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS

In lexical presupposition, the speakers' statement stands for another idea. Here the condition of truth information is not necessary. In assertive verb, the state of being implied to say someone to do something and verbs attempt to trigger that something tried to do are included. The asserted meaning is that the person succeeded in doing something. Therefore, in saying someone did not manage to do something, the asserted purpose is that the person failed, whereas the presupposed meaning (non-asserted) is that the person tried to do that something (Yule, 1996). Pavlick and Burch (2016) have combined the idea of entailment with implicative or assertive verbs. Avoided, forgot to, ought to have, happened to, intended to, managed, remember, and forget are lexical presupposition triggers.

III.III. FACTIVE ITEMS

In factive verbs, we check the classification of verbs. Our focus is on the information written after the verb. These verbs take a complement clause which is considered valid (Gutschera, 1978). These triggers are: know, appreciate, saw, forced to, agree, make sense, amuse, glad, grasp, and bear in mind.

III.IV. NON-FACTIVE

Non-factive presupposition is about the condition that is contrary to the truth condition. Yule (1996) gave verbs like dream, imagine and pretend under non-factive presupposition triggers. These verbs are used as the "presupposition that is not true."

III.V. STRUCTURAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGER

The information presented in this structure is necessarily accurate. Here "wh" family words are used in the sense of asking questions (Yule, 2006), so these triggers categories are "wh questions". In this, the information found after the question is valid. Structural presupposition triggers are when, where, and who.

III.VI. COUNTER FACTUAL CONDITIONALS

The information in the if-clause is not accurate at the time of utterance. What is presupposed is false and counter to the fact (Khaleel, 2010). These clauses start with "if". According to Fillmore (1969), "one must mention that an utterance of the sentence presupposes the falsity of the proposition contained in the if-clause." Numerous research studies have been conducted on the analysis of presupposition triggers. For example, Grundy (2008) investigated the types of presupposition triggers in the conversation of native children of the English community. He concluded that small native children were habitual of using "some" and "any" which trigger the existence of presupposition behind those words. Pang (2016) also examined presupposition triggers as linguistic features of print advertising language. Furthermore, Liang and Liu (2016) investigated the use of lexical and syntactical presupposition triggers in the political speech of Hilary.

In 2016, Pang investigated presupposition triggers as linguistic features of print advertising language. He further divided and analyzed those triggers according to the two categories of presupposition triggers a) lexical presupposition triggers and b) syntactical presupposition triggers. They included definite description, factive verb, implicative verbs, change of state verbs, verbs of judging, and iterative into lexical presupposition triggers. He further added temporal clauses, cleft sentences, implicit clefts with stressed constituents, and comparison and contrast in syntactic presupposition triggers. He concluded that both types of presupposition triggers were helpful in understanding the meanings of particular lexical items and syntactic constructions used in print advertising language. In the same year, Liang and Liu (2016) investigated the use of lexical and syntactical presupposition triggers in the political speech of Hilary. They noted that Hilary tried to mold the audience's minds through presupposition triggers. These triggers provide a direction to readers' interpretation so anyone can establish a favorable or unfavorable opinion towards politician's activities while simply reading them. Their findings proved that throughout her messages, she used both types of presupposition triggers and these triggers provided her

language a vivid and robust position which helped her to establish a strong connection between the audience and speaker. She played well with these presupposition triggers in her political speeches. Grundy (2008) has investigated the importance of background in the comprehension of presupposition in his research study. He believes that understanding information is established with its background as these accommodations are part of a specific grammatical or lexical item (Grundy, 2008). Stalnaker (cited in Khaleel, 2010) has also provided his concept of background. He said that speakers understand presupposition due to its background information because they can fully understand the meanings of a conversation with its background knowledge. Consequently, it can be said that background provides support in disclosing the intentions of presupposition triggers. In the research studies mentioned above, presupposition triggers are explored chiefly in newspapers or classroom discourses. However, there are other untouched genres in our community which are not explored from this point of view. For instance, political autobiographies are not examined for this purpose. Generally, discourses with political perspectives are written with a particular purpose. The writers of such discourses are experts in using language to reflect their political and personal thoughts. They know how to use words to influence people. They can persuade people through their discourses. It has been seen that many politicians have used various components of pragmatics like implicature, deixis, and presupposition in their writings (Smahyeeen & Latiff, 2018), so these pragmatics elements should be considered.

To our knowledge, researchers have not yet discussed the uses and functions of presupposition triggers in political memoirs. Therefore, the notion discussed in this research paper was the recognition of types and functions of presupposition triggers used in Pakistani political memoirs. Writers adopt variant ways to use presupposition triggers in their memoirs. These triggers are context-dependent as they communicate writers' specific ideas hidden behind their pieces of work. Sometimes memoirs are mixed with autobiographies; however memoirs are a sub-genre of them. Investigation of presupposition triggers in political memoirs remained an innovative study for researchers and linguists. The components of my theoretical background were the presupposition triggers proposed by Yule (1996). This theoretical framework was suitable for this research work because it focused on highlighting the meanings of presupposition triggers. In the present research, researchers had investigated recurrent presupposition triggers used by Pakistani writers in their political memoirs. The analysis of presupposition triggers in Pakistani political memoirs provided researchers with first-hand knowledge of writers' unique writing styles and approaches of mind.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The present study had a corpus pragmatic approach to analyzing presupposition triggers in Pakistani political memoirs. The researchers had utilized the methodology of corpus linguistics to explore these presupposition triggers contextually in the memoirs of Imran Khan and Pervaiz Musharaf (Rühlemann & Clancy, 2018). Corpus pragmatic blends form and function, so in this integrated reading methodology (Rühlemann & Aijmer 2015; Ali and Audi, 2016; Ali and Audi, 2018; Sajid and Ali, 2018; Mehmood et al., 2022; Senturk and Ali, 2021) the focus was on both "horizontal reading methodology of pragmatic analysis and vertical reading methodology of corpus linguistics" (Rühlemann & Clancy, 2018). We deduced it as mixed-method research. In this study, Yule (1996) proposed presupposition triggers were used as theoretical background. The present study aimed to explain presupposition triggers contextually and point out their various functions in Pakistani political memoirs.

A descriptive research design was selected because the purpose of the study was to describe those presupposition triggers contextually used by Pakistani writers in their political memoirs. According to Glatthorn and Joyner (2003), a descriptive research discusses the present phenomenon at the description level. According to this definition, the present study was descriptive by nature. Firstly, researchers prepared “mark files” of Pakistani political memoirs while cleaning, saving, and changing data in .txt document to explore presupposition triggers contextually. Secondly, these files were uploaded to AntConc 3.5.8, a corpus tool, to select presupposition triggers. At the third step, those collected presupposition triggers were explored and analyzed qualitatively. The types and functions of presupposition triggers were interpreted in words. We found 2806 presupposition triggers from the corpus. However, we selected through convenient sampling only 2 to 3 presupposition triggers from each category of Yule’s (1996) theory of presupposition triggers. The study's findings and conclusions were drawn based on data analysis and discussion.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the analysis of both political memoirs, researchers found that several presupposition triggers were used in both texts with different frequencies. This study classified these triggers according to the presented presupposition triggers of Yule (1996). Table 1 shows the frequency of each presupposition trigger in both memoirs. Further, these triggers provided different meanings according to their pragmatic context. The selected presupposition triggers are mentioned clearly in table no 1.

Table 1: Presupposition Triggers

No	Presupposition triggers	Presupposition triggers selected from both memoirs	Frequency	
			A1	A2
1	Existential presupposition triggers	Mine	11	11
		His	409	611
		Ours	3	6
2	Lexical presupposition triggers	Avoided to	2	1
		Happened to	10	6
		Managed to	6	23
3	Factive items	Know	51	66
		Saw	45	1
4	Non factive items	Dreamed	1	1
		Imagined	1	3
5	Structural presupposition triggers	Where	1	3
		Who	1	2
6	Counter factual conditionals	If clause	154	164

V.I. EXISTENTIAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS

The first presupposition trigger Yule (1996) presented is existential presupposition triggers. These triggers assume the existence of the entities, so we get information about them. According to the table 1 this trigger was used at the maximum level in both the texts; however they vary in their function or contextual meanings.

Table 2: Existential Presupposition Trigger

Existential Presupposition triggers		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan uses	Mine	Personal life
	His	Religious
	Ours	Historical
Pervaiz Musharaf uses	Mine	Political
	His	Terrorism
	Ours	Political

The first existential presupposition trigger used by Imran Khan is “mine”. Its analysis reveals that he used this trigger to cover an incident from his personal life. In a memoir it is also necessary to cover the personal incidents of

the persons, mentioned in the memoirs. The context of this trigger explains Imran's travelling overseas for completing his degree. He writes,

“... similar family structure to **mine**, and had like me been to a private, English-language school.”

Here, the author tries to bring a personal event from the adulthood of Imran Khan into the attention of the audience. Being elder son of the family he went abroad to pursue his education and he made Vikram Mehta, an elder son of an Indian family, his friend. As both had similar family backgrounds, Imran felt relax in his company. The context reveals that both spent time together and built their sweet memories. The second selected existential presupposition trigger was “his” and researchers found that writer wanted to show his religious bent of mind to the readers through this trigger.

“... partially through **his** ability to occasionally foresee some pitfalls but mainly because of his great wisdom that never cease to amaze me.”

Imran Khan has used this trigger to show his respect towards Main Bashir, a religious scholar. Imran Khan revealed in his memoir that he never remained religious in early days of his life so when he turned towards religion this credit went to some religious personalities and one of them was Main Bashir. On the behalf of this trigger the writer is showing a religious change in his personality due to the impressive personality of Main Bashir whom he met at the house of his friend. He described his personality while saying that he looked like a common with a vast religious knowledge and insight. The context of this trigger also reveals that Imran Khan was impressed of Main Bashir's wisdom because he had the ability to foresee some pitfall. The next existential presupposition trigger is “ours” which covers a historical reference.

“Though Iqbal lived in a historical context that was different from **ours** in several ways...”

Through this presupposition trigger, Imran Khan has shown the teachings of Iqbal and the demands of new world. Further, he mentions that Iqbal lived in totally a different world from us, however his teachings are relevant to us. Iqbal's ideology is a guideline for us so while acting upon his teachings we can bring positive changes in our people and society.

The same existential presupposition triggers were used in the memoir of Pervaiz Musharaf, however they conveyed different meanings. For instance, through “mine” he has covered an incident of political conspiracy. He writes in his memoir,

“General Ziauddin's name for **mine**, and bring it to him for signature.”

Pervaiz Musaraf wanted to make readers realize that Nawaz Sharif played a political game against him. Nawaz Sharif wanted to stop the removal of Musharaf's predecessor, General Ziauddin, so he ordered the military secretary to replace Musharaf's name with his predecessor. He also ordered him to change the date in the document and took his sign on it. Nawaz Sharif undertook that decision because General Ziauddin was a hand puppet of him who obeyed his all orders. Consequently, the news of his removal was shocking for him so he played this game to save him from termination.

Pervaiz Musharaf used next presupposition trigger “his” to highlight an incident of terrorism. His linguistic construction reveals the motives of Omar Sheikh, a terrorist, in kidnapping Pearl.

“He told Adil about **his** abduction plan.”

He mentioned in his memoir that Omar Sheikh shared his plan of abduction with Adil Shiekh. Omar Sheikh was thinking big so he prepared a plan of kidnapping Pearl. On telling the abduction plan, Adil also became excited to take part in that plan. A final meeting was organized among Omar Sheikh, Ahmed bhai and Adil to fulfill that plan.

Through next existential presupposition triggers “our”, Pervaiz Musharaf highlighted the strong position of Pakistan while competing with India. He narrates,

“...we could threaten more sensitive objectives of the enemy than they could of **ours**, and in less time.”

The construction “our” presupposed that both the countries, Pakistan and India, were threatening one another. Musharaf further mentioned that Pakistan was in better condition to give threat to India rather they receiving threat from them.

V.II. LEXICAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS

Researchers also found lexical presupposition triggers in the texts of both memoirs however their use was much less than the frequency of existential presupposition triggers. These triggers convey the implicit meanings in the best way and both writers have used these triggers in their memoirs.

Table 3: Lexical Presupposition Trigger

Lexical Presupposition triggers		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan uses	Avoided	Personal
	Happened to	Personal
	Managed to	Traditional
Pervaiz Musaraf uses	Avoided	Political
	Happened to	Political
	Managed to	Inflation

Imran Khan has used first lexical presupposition trigger “avoided” to bring forward his memories as a cricketer.

“For days afterwards we all **avoided** going out in public to escape the inevitable backlash.”

This trigger presupposed the face saving act of Imran Khan after losing their match with India. During his youth time when he was a cricketer they lost a match in India so Imran Khan and his entourage avoided going outside to avoid public criticism. They knew that public remains always ready to criticize the weaknesses of people so they kept themselves away from the people.

The second lexical presupposition trigger used in Imran Khan’s memoir was “happened to” and it presupposed another personal incident of his life.

“... air-conditioning contract to the lowest bidder, who **happened to** be a friend of mine, Irshad Khan.”

According to this trigger, Irshad Khan became Imran’s friend by coincident. He came to Imran to give him feedback on the construction committee's performance in failing to pass the contract for air conditioning in Imran Khan's hospital. Actually, he exhibited the corrupt picture of construction committee before him that was habitual of leaving projects undone previously. He further guided that selection of this construction committee was a matter of conspiracy against Imran Khan’s hospital building.

The third selected lexical presupposition trigger was “managed”.

“We have actually **managed** to engineer a mini-revolution, with conservative families ...”

This lexical presupposition trigger “managed” explains the desires and fears of individuals of Waziristan who had many fears of educating their daughters. People of Waziristan desired to get their daughters knowledgeable however they had also a notion about western education which could spoil their daughters. Imran Khan highlighted through this trigger that he brought revolution while establishing NUML University in their area where people of Waziristan could send their daughters and sons to get education.

Pervaiz Musharaf has also utilized these lexical presupposition triggers in his memoir keeping with to his own will.

“For years, our leaders had **avoided** any institutional checks and had misgoverned the nation with impunity.”

The first lexical presupposition trigger is “avoided” and its context shows the overall mindset of Pakistani politician. Pakistani economic system became scattered because of their behavior. Government should take a look at establishments however they no longer care about it.

The subsequent lexical trigger is “happened to” and its context exhibits that Director General was in Washington by chance. Director General updated Musharaf about his meeting with U.S Deputy Secretary who warned him that Pakistan became terrorist country while supporting them so it must equipped ready for US attack.

“Islamabad the next day, our director general of Inter Services Intelligence, who **happened to** be in Washington...”

The next lexical presupposition trigger “managed” reveals the inflation condition in Pakistan during Pervaiz Musharaf time. Pervaiz Musharaf exhibited that prices of the useable entities were growing including petroleum, tea and edible oil however they had reduced the expense of debt servicing.

“... and as mentioned earlier, we **managed** to achieve that reduction.”

V.III. FACTIVE ITEMS

Researchers observed that third category of presupposition trigger, factive items, were used extensively in both memoirs. The selected fative items are,

Table 4: Factive Items

Factive Items		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan	Know	Cultural
	Saw	Religious
Pervaiz Musaraf	Know	Terrorism
	Saw	9/11 terrorism

Factive items presuppose the truth of their complement clause. The first factive item “know” used by Imran Khan depicts the culture of Pakistan.

“Traditional families will most likely **know** a groom's entire background.”

Here, the complement clause of “know” explains the system of arranged marriages in Pakistani culture. Imran Khan triggered that in arranged marriages the parents inquire about the background of the groom. This thing also revealed that in Pakistani marriages no importance is given to the likeness of bride and groom and all matters are settled by the parents.

The second factive item is “saw” and its complement clause covers Imran Khan’s definition of Islam. Through the contextual analysis of this presupposition trigger, he provides the true picture of implementation of Islam in Europe. He further explained that people in Europe acted according to the principles of Islam without any propaganda because they were true followers of it.

“...I saw no Muslims in Europe but I **saw** a lot of Islam.' and of his Homeland”.

Researchers observed that Imran Khan used “know” to show the culture of Pakistan, on the contrary, Pervaiz Musharaf triggered presupposition of a terrorist attack through it.

“... we nabbed three men who told us what we needed to **know**.”

Here, know Pervaiz Musharaf wanted to collect information about Mustafa Muhammad (KSM) so they started investigation from three men in the old fashioned manner. They arranged a proper but old fashioned investigation to find KSM.

The next factive item is “saw” and Pervaiz Mushraf has used this trigger to cover another terrorism incident.

“I could not believe what I **saw**.”

The most horrible and historical changing incident of 9//11 is covered through this trigger. The context of “saw” shows that Musharaf noticed something on television on the demand of his military secretary. When he opened TV, he saw smoke that was coming outside of World Trade Center and people were jumping from the windows. Later he came to know that some terrorists attacked World Trade Center and burnt it.

V.IV. NON- FACTIVE ITEMS

The fourth presupposition trigger was factive items. These triggers indicated some personal and political incidents. Both politicians used these triggers in their memoirs and their contextual meanings are given in table 5.

Table 5: Non- factive Items

Non factive Items		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan uses	Dreamed	Personal
	Imagined	Political
Pervaiz Musaraf uses	Dreamed	Personal
	Imagined	Political

These triggers were used least in both the texts. Through first non-factive item “dreamed” Imran Khan showed his personal habit. He wanted to tell the audience that he always remained a critic of his own deeds so on finding his bowling style faulty, he concentrated on its solution and he became successful in finding the solution of his faulty bowling in one of his dreams.

“Such was my concentration that I **dreamed** and saw myself bowling and worked ...”

The next non-factive item, selected from the memoir of Imran Khan, was “imagined” and it presupposed a political manner.

“I **imagined** a whole day must have passed only to realize that about ...”

Once Imran Khan was imprisoned and his feelings of boredom were covered through this trigger. During that time Imran Khan had to spend his life alone so he got bored in the jail. To spend his day he counted hours in jail.

Musharaf also approached “dreamed” in personal manner.

“ I **dreamed** of my parents' comfortable home in Karachi, St. Patrick's, FC College...”

It presupposed an incident of ragging of Pervaiz Musharaf . When this incident happened, Pervaiz Musharaf was not at home but he was in a hostel. He recalled his ragging on the first night at boarding school so he missed his home that night.

Musharaf showed the irresponsible nature of Dr. Abdul Qadeer Khan through second non-factive item “imagined”. He explained to the audience that Dr. A. Q Khan was an irresponsible person so Musharaf was not sure about his making of bomb himself. Further, Musharaf he did not consider him a scientist.

“...given to A.Q. Nobody ever **imagined** how irresponsible and reckless he could be.”

V.V. STRUCTURAL PRESUPPOSITION TRIGGERS

Structural presupposition trigger were also used by both politicians, however they utilized those triggers according to their own bent of mind. Researchers found that Pervaiz Mushraf pointed out political events from these triggers while Imran Khan gave different shades apart from politics to these triggers.

Table 6: Structural Presupposition Triggers

Structural Presupposition Triggers		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan uses	Where	Pakistani people reaction
	Who	Pakistan beauty
Pervaiz Musaraf uses	Where	Political
	Who	Political

It is indicated in table 1, structural presupposition constructions were found among the least frequent categories of presupposition in both the memoirs. The first structural presupposition trigger starts with “where”.

“... it could have been anyone's – so **where** was the army?”

Imran Khan has used this structure to presuppose the questioning reaction of Pakistani people against army passive role in the US search plan of Usama bin Laden in Pakistan. Its context explains that US helicopters were bombing on buildings near the army’s academy so they could search and find Usama bin Laden but Pakistani army was unable to save the Pakistani citizen as army might be busy in somewhere else. This thing made people against army and for the first time they questioned about the role of army as their protector who could not save them from US bombing.

The second structural presupposition trigger “who” presuppose the existence of the beautiful natural places of Pakistan in Imran Khan memoir.

“**Who** knows how many such idyllic places still exist there?”

The analysis of this trigger reports the beauty of Pakistan. Imran Khan writes that Pakistan is full of significant beautiful places and areas, however many people are unaware of them so they have not explored these areas yet.

Pervaiz Mushraf has brought forth political ideas through both of structural presupposition triggers.

“**Where can we go?**” I asked the pilot.

Musharaf disclosed the conspiracy of Nawaz Sharif against him through first structure. The context shows that Nawaz Sharif made arrangement to hijack Musharaf’s plane to send him to India. When he asked from Pilot where his plane could be landed, pilot told that he was not allowed to land his plane in Pakistan. Musharaf got angrier to listen that because they could only land in India.

“**Who was to be the president of the party?** I felt very honored when ...”

The next structural presupposition trigger starts with “who” and Pervaiz Musharaf wanted to show the audience the need of a party leader for Muslim League. Muslim league needed a president badly, so they all agreed that Musharaf could select any president for them.

V.VI. COUNTER FACTUAL CONDITIONALS

Additionally, researchers found counter factual conditional in both the memoirs with the second highest frequency. A counter factual conditional show that information mentioned in if clause structure is not true at the time of speaking (Yule, 1996). The analysis of these structures in the memoirs of Imran Khan and Pervaiz Musharaf is mentioned below.

Table 7: Counter Factual Conditional

Counter Factual Conditionals		Contextual Meanings
Imran Khan uses	If a captain...	Personal
	If anyone puts...	Religious
Pervaiz Musaraf uses	if a bomb could ...	Western world biasness
	If Afghanistan was ...	Terrorism

“If a captain shows any weakness or buckles under pressure, the team collapses, and I knew that without ...”

The first counter factual conditional presupposes Imran Khan’s firmness as a team captain.

Being a captain Imran had to show good performance so he could boost up the moral of team.

This is a fact if team leader comes under pressure then whole team suffers, therefore he did not show any weakness. He did not show any weakness being captain of his team rather he uplifted the moral of his team while praising them.

“As the Quran says **'If anyone puts his trust in Allah sufficient is He for him.'**

The context of the next trigger covers Islamic ideology of Imran Khan. Imran Khan pointed out the importance of believes in Allah. The first half of the sentence provides a condition of sufficiency of Allah for one. He reveals that in the last two years of his career he used to play internationally to raise funds for his hospital because his believe became firm in Allah. He knew that success and humiliation is in the hands of Allah.

Pervaiz Musharaf used first “if clause” structure to disclose the conspiracy of powerful countries against Islam and Muslim countries.

“... to our public and to the world **_as if a bomb could have a religion.**”

The trigger presupposes that “Bombs” do not have any religion. However, in May 1998, Dr. A. Q Khan became the father of Islamic bomb. When he made an atomic weapon, bomb, the western world gave his bomb a name. Although bombs do not have any religion but when it comes to Muslim country then all become biased.

“Everyone was rightly concerned that **if Afghanistan was bombed...**”

In next utterance, Musharaf shows that Afghanistan was not bombed still. However, if that had happened, then many innocent people might have died. Musharaf was hesitant to advice people who should talk to Mullah Omer to get rid of Osama bin Laden from his country.

VI. CONCLUSION

After analyzing presupposition triggers from both the political memoirs, researchers came to this conclusion that both the writers have provided their intended information to their readers through these triggers. Their use in political memoirs assists the readers to understand the communicated message of the writers and keep their interest high. Both the writers have used these presupposition triggers in their memoirs however some differences were noted in their frequency of use and their functions. The difference in the use of these presupposition triggers in the memoirs highlights writers' attitudes toward the treatment of some linguistic constructions. Overall existential presupposition trigger was used at the highest level in both the memoirs. Counter factual conditional and factive items were also used at maximum level. The other remaining presupposition triggers: lexical presupposition trigger, structural presupposition trigger and non-factive items were occurred with less frequency in both the texts. At the same time, researchers also found that Pervaiz Musharaf had used more presupposition triggers in his memoir than Imran Khan. However, factive item was occurred more in Imran Khan's memoir. This variation in the frequency of use shows the difference in the writing style of the both the writers. From above mentioned discussion part, a clear difference can be observed in the conveying of meanings (functions) of presupposition triggers. These triggers were explored within their particular contexts so they had provided various types of meanings. The contexts of these triggers had provided various meaning to them. Researchers found that Pakistani politicians mostly used these triggers to point out some political and personal incidents from their lives. Pervaiz Musharaf used these triggers to indicate more political events than Imran Khan. At the same time, researchers also found variety in their functions in the memoir of Imran Khan. The major functions of Pervaiz Musharaf memoir were politics, personal incidents, and terrorism. On the other hand, Imran Khan used these triggers in political, personal, cultural, traditional, religious and historical contexts. So researchers were able to find a few common and many various individual functions of these triggers in both memoirs. This thing has provided individuality to the writing styles of both writers of the selected Pakistani political memoirs.

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